

KNOWLEDGE ON SUBJECT-VERB AGREEMENT AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS: BASIS FOR REMEDIAL SUBJECT OFFERINGS

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Knowledge on Subject-Verb Agreement among College Students: Basis for Remedial Subject Offerings

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Abstract

This study explores the knowledge of subject-verb agreement among college students as a basis for remedial subject offerings. The research examines the relationship between students' demographic profiles, their perceptions of English as a subject, and their proficiency in subject-verb agreement rules. A quantitative descriptive research method was employed, utilizing statistical tools such as percentage, frequency, weighted mean, and chi-square to analyze responses collected through a questionnaire. Findings indicate that most respondents are female, aged 18-19, and rely primarily on mobile devices as learning resources. Students demonstrated an overall satisfactory level of understanding of subject-verb agreement rules, excelling in areas such as singular and plural verb usage, indefinite pronouns, and specific noun-verb relationships. However, weaknesses were observed in rules concerning collective nouns and numerical expressions. The study also found that students' subject-verb agreement knowledge is not significantly influenced by their age, sex, or available learning resources but is affected by their perception of English. Based on these findings, the study recommends the development of Course Syllabi and Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) tailored to address students' weaknesses in subject-verb agreement. These materials should provide clear explanations, detailed examples, and structured exercises to reinforce learning. The modules can be utilized in remedial classes to enhance students' proficiency. This research highlights the need for targeted interventions to improve English grammar competency, ensuring better academic performance and communication skills among college students.

Keywords: *subject-verb agreement, english proficiency, college students, remedial instruction, grammar knowledge, quantitative research*

Introduction

Linguistics is a profound field that reveals the intricacies of language and its influence on our everyday experiences. By exploring the scientific examination of language, a person acquires a more profound comprehension of how language enables efficient communication, conserves cultural traditions, molds cognitive growth, and fosters professional advancement. Nordquist (2020) stated that the grammar of a language includes basic axioms such as verb tenses, articles and adjectives (and their proper order), how questions are phrased, and much more. Language cannot function without grammar. It would simply make no sense—people require grammar to communicate effectively.

In the Philippines, English has long been a part of the curriculum of various academic programs. Despite the economic benefits of being an English-speaking nation, Filipinos have not fully maximized its potentials. According to Valderama (2019), there was an article that shows Filipinos are declining in English proficiency. The Philippines placed from 14th in 2018 to 20th in the year 2019. English Proficiency Index (EPI) is said to measure the average level of the English language skills of language learners based on the results of an online Standard English Test (SET). This was administered by a Swiss-based global company focusing on language, academic, cultural exchange, and educational travel programs, named English Proficiency Education First. The country's English Proficiency Index (EPI) is believed to be a good reason why the country's education sector should worry and address this concern immediately.

One researcher who has relatively spent years in the English language teaching career has noted that one of the main problems of the students is their functional grasp of subject-verb agreement. ESL students' problematic difficulties in their use of subject-verb agreement are becoming more obvious and rampant, and it cuts across the different grade levels where students belong. From the primary school towards the university level, many students are noted in their speech and writing as not being able to abide with the rules of subject-verb agreement. Errors on subject-verb agreement were found not only in students' essays but even in writings of colleagues in universities. The more worrisome dimension of this problem is that such fiasco extends even to professionals who use English in their lectures or those among the honorable members of state and national assemblies or those engaged in varied media outfits. Errors in subject-verb agreement are becoming wide spread and it seems as if many people are either no longer aware of the rules or they simply undermine the importance of grammar rules, for as long as they are able to convey their message (Tafida & Okunade, 2016 as cited by Cabaltica and Osabel, 2021).

The research proponent seeks to identify and understand the level of knowledge that college students possess concerning subject-verb agreement and desires to know how good they are on this topic.

It is in this context that the researcher is conducting such study in order to propose intervention program based on the result of the study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the knowledge on S-V agreement among college students of Villaflores College, Tanjay City. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. available learning resources at home?
2. What is the extent of perception of students towards English subject in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive factors;
 - 2.2. behavioral factors; and
 - 2.3. environmental factors?
3. What is the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement according to the following rules when:
 - 3.1. A verb should agree with its subject in number;
 - 3.2. One of two subjects is joined by or, nor or but;
 - 3.3. Indefinite pronouns are used as subjects of the sentence like every, each, everyone, everybody, everything, nobody, nothing, no one, anyone, anybody, anything, someone, somebody, and something;
 - 3.4. A singular subject followed immediately by as well as, in addition to, no less than, with, together with, or a similar construction;
 - 3.5. A collective noun is used in the sentence;
 - 3.6. Some nouns end in -s even though they are considered singular;
 - 3.7. Quantities and some or multiples of numbers are used in the sentence; and
 - 3.8. The sentence has “the number” and “a number.”
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement?
6. What program/project could be designed to enhance the S-V agreement knowledge of the students?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive-correlational method, which is designed to determine whether two or more variables are associated with each other. A descriptive method was employed to determine the profile of the respondents and the extent of perception of students towards English subject and the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement. On the other hand, the correlational method was used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement and a significant relationship between the perception of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the college students of Villaflores College, Tanjay City with a total number of 367 learners. The respondents come from the following college departments:

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents (N= 367)*

<i>Department</i>	<i>Number of College Learners</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	95	25.89
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	191	52.04
Bachelor of Elementary Education	28	7.63
Bachelor of Secondary Education	53	14.44
Total	367	100

Instrument

The research questionnaire was crafted by the researcher for the specific purpose of ascertaining data relevant to the research questions and hypotheses posed to address the stated research problem. The survey questionnaire was composed of 3 important parts: Part I - Profile of the respondents; Part II – Extent of perception of college students towards English subject; and Part III- Extent of Knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement.

Procedure

The gathering of research data was done using the researcher-made questionnaire. Moreover, the following procedures were followed:

(1) A letter was sent to the Dean of the different college departments of Villaflores College; (2) With the approval of the Dean from the different college departments, the researcher then distributed the questionnaires to the respondents personally; and (3) The researcher collect the questionnaires from the respondents and then checked if all questions were answered.

Data Analysis

The responses from the questionnaire were statistically analyzed. The following statistical tools were used:

Problem 1 employs frequency distribution, percentage, and rank to determine the profile of the respondents. Frequency distribution is a representation that displays the number of observations within a given interval. The representation of a frequency distribution in this study is tabular so that it is easier to understand. The percentage was computed utilizing dividing the total number of responses to a specific question by the total number of respondents multiplied by 100, as shown in the formula. The deals with one's position or status of the response. It refers to a position within a hierarchy of the results.

Problems 2 and 3 employ the weighted mean with the Likert's scale and rank to determine the extent of perception of college students towards English subject and knowledge of students on the subject-verb agreement. The following formula was used for the calculation of the weighted mean.

Problems 4 and 5 utilized the chi-square to determine the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement and the significant relationship between the perception of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the results of the research study. The presentation of the findings follows the order of the problems covered in this study for purposes of identity and clarity. Upon the retrieval of the questionnaires, the responses are tabulated. Analysis of the data start after the data was computed. To make the data more presentable, the researcher uses tables.

Table 2.1. *Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age (N=367)*

Age (In Years)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
18-19	305	83.11	1
20-21	47	12.81	2
22-23	7	1.91	3
24-25	2	0.54	5
26 and above	6	1.63	4
Total	367	100.00	
= 19.00 \bar{X}			

Table 2.1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The data show that the majority of the respondents fall within the 18–19 age bracket with a frequency of 305 or 83.11%. This is followed by the 20-21 years old age bracket with a frequency of 47 or 12.81%. The 22–23 age bracket has a frequency of 7 or 1.91% and the 26 and above bracket comprises a frequency of 6 or 1.63%. Finally, the 24–25 age bracket has the lowest frequency of 2 or 0.54%.

The findings above show that the majority of the 1st year college students in Villaflores College have the 18-19 years old age bracket with a frequency of 305 or 83.11% as the ideal age for 1st year college students in the Philippine Educational system. In contrast, the lowest frequency is 6 or 1.63% which belongs to 26 and above age bracket.

DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019, which outlines the policy guidelines for the K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines, does not specify a strict age for first-year college students. Secondary Education is composed of two key stages of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, namely, Junior High School comprising Grade 7 to 8, and Senior High School covering Grade 11 to 12. Learners in Secondary Education are generally from 12 to 17 years old. Therefore, Filipino students typically enter college around the age of 18.

The results conform to the study of Cayaon (2022) where it was found out 70% of the respondents were in the age of 17-18. The data showed that the average age of the respondents was 17.5.

Table 2.2. *Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Sex (N=367)*

Sex	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Male	182	49.59	2
Female	185	50.41	1
Total	367	100.00	

Table 2.2 reveals the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. Out of 367 respondents, 182 respondents belong to the male group or 49.59%; and 185 respondents belong to the female group or 50.41%. This means that most of the respondents are female.

This result conformed to the study of Cebu (2023) where it was found out in his study that most of the Filipino college students are

females with 53% of the total respondents. Another study of Cayaon (2022) revealed that as to the gender of the respondents, the majority (66.67%) of the respondents are females while 33.33% are males.

The 2020 Global Gender Gap Report by the World Economic Forum highlighted that 71.3% of Filipino women were enrolled in secondary education and 40.4% in tertiary education, compared to 60.2% and 40.4% for men, respectively. This indicates a higher female enrollment rate at both high school and college levels (Cruz, 2019).

Table 2.3. *Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Available Learning Resources at Home*

<i>Resources</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Textbooks	109	29.70	2
Dictionaries	75	20.41	4
Laptop	82	22.34	3
Desktop	28	7.63	5
Tablet	27	7.36	6
Smartphone	341	92.92	1

Table 2.3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of available learning resources at home. Smartphones are the most accessible resource, with a frequency of 341 or 92.92% ranking it first. Textbooks rank second with a frequency of 109 or 29.70%; laptops are third with a frequency of 82 or 22.34%; dictionaries are fourth with a frequency of 75 or 20.41%; followed by desktops with a frequency of 28 or 7.63%; and lastly tablets with a frequency of 27 or 7.36%.

Investigating further the results, smartphones are overwhelmingly the most accessible learning resource with a frequency of 341 or 92.92% suggesting that smartphones are essential for studying at home. On the other hand, tablets are the least accessible, with only 27 respondents or 7.36% possibly indicating a lower preference or need for tablets when other /versatile devices like smartphones and laptops are available.

A related study can support this part of the analysis, which found that mobile technology has spread rapidly around the globe. More than 5 billion individuals are expected to own mobile devices today, with smartphones accounting for more than half of these connections (Silver, 2019). The Diffusion of Innovation Theory can also support the findings, which explains how, through time, technological innovations such as gadgets, tools, and other technologies can gain popularity among media consumers and spread through a specific population (LaMorte, 2019).

Table 3.1. *Extent of Perception of Students Towards English Subject in Terms of Cognitive Factors*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. Learning English for me is a pride.	3.63	Agree	9
2. Learning English enables me to consider new perspectives.	3.84	Agree	7
3. Learning English boosts my confidence.	3.99	Agree	5
4. English subject has a substance that covers numerous fields of learning.	3.68	Agree	8
5. By mastering English, I can easily learn other lessons well.	3.95	Agree	6
6. I believe that listening, speaking, reading, and writing are all important in learning English.	4.33	Strongly Agree	2
7. I believe that learning English will enhance my personality.	4.14	Agree	3
8. I believe that learning English is important for my future career.	4.34	Strongly Agree	1
9. Grammatical rules and vocabulary development can be learned in the English subject.	4.08	Agree	4
10. I see English as a difficult subject to be learned.	3.34	Neutral	10
Average Weighted Mean	3.93	Agree	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree | 3.41 – 4.20 Agree | 2.61 – 3.40 Undecided | 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree | 1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As presented in Table 3.1, the extent of perception of students towards English subject in terms of cognitive factors obtained an average weighted mean of 3.93, with a verbal description of “agree.”

Investigating further the results, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.34 on item no. 8, which states “I believe that learning English is important for my future career” with verbal description of “strongly disagree.” In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.34 is on item no. 10, which states “I see English as a difficult subject to be learned” with a verbal description of “agree.”

Results in this regard imply that students’ learning could become more enjoyable if they are engaged in practical activities that can catch their attention and interest. The students can feel less scared and more motivated to learn the English subject by using more interesting activities such as involving them in English games, group sessions or other entertaining activities. Furthermore, students may find English less difficult to learn if they are involved in learning experiences that are based on real-life situations.

The result conform to the study of Pratiwi et. al (2020). According to them, the other main factor inhibiting the students in speaking is also revealed in the findings of their research and it is called as cognitive factor. Grammar error, pronunciation problems, and

vocabulary are the sub-factors inhibiting students in speaking as found in the research findings. Grammar turns out to be the inhibiting factor giving its big influence to the students in learning to speak English.

Table 3.2. *Extent of Perception of Students Towards English Subject in Terms of Behavioral Factors*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. I like to speak English in the class.	3.32	Neutral	5
2. I feel ashamed to speak English in front of the class.	3.29	Neutral	7
3. Speaking English anywhere makes me feel anxious.	3.21	Neutral	8
4. I am afraid of committing grammatical mistakes whenever I speak in front of other people.	3.77	Agree	2.5
5. I often procrastinate when it comes to doing my English homework.	3.30	Neutral	6
6. I never asked for homework or additional assignments to the teacher if I was not present in class.	2.61	Neutral	10
7. I do not feel enthusiastic to come to class during my English class.	2.74	Neutral	9
8. I like to listen to my English teacher during the discussion.	4.00	Agree	1
9. I enjoy studying English.	3.77	Agree	2.5
10. I always participate in my English class.	3.59	Agree	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.36	Neutral	

The results in Table 3.2 disclosed that the respondents assessed an average weighted mean of 3.36 in extent of perception of students towards English subject in terms of behavioral factors, with a verbal description of “neutral.”

Remarkably, students give emphasis on item no. 8, “I like to listen to my English teacher during the discussion,” with a mean score of 4.00, with a verbal description of “agree.” In contrast, the lowest mean score is item no. 6, which is on “I never asked for homework or additional assignments to the teacher if I was not present in class,” which was rated 2.61, and with a verbal description of “neutral.”

Based on the results, it can be suggested that students need to develop a stronger sense of responsibility for the given tasks. They may feel unsure or hesitant to ask their teachers for any missed homework, the teachers must be there to encourage and motivate their learners on how to catch up all those missed homework. The English teacher can help by motivating students to take initiative, guiding them to actively manage their own learning to ensure progress in daily task.

This result conform the study of Ansow et. al. (2022) that most of the respondents remain neutral and when asked whether they frequently used the language at school and with people, or used with people they frequently met or with their teachers and classmates, and more than half of the respondents have positive behavior toward English learning. However, it should be noted that some of them are in doubt about learning the language.

Another study by Nguyen and Pham (2020) revealed that the respondents show a neutral behavioral attitude towards learning English. Students like to do some activities when studying in English classes such as giving opinion and practicing English with other learners. However, they are not comfortable whenever they are speaking English.

Table 3.3. *Extent of Perception of Students Towards English Subject in Terms of Environmental Factors*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. I have English reading materials available at home.	3.38	Neutral	8
2. I am motivated to learn English because I dream to live abroad.	3.62	Agree	6
3. I like to learn English because the arrangements of seats, learning environment, and classroom dynamics are interesting to me.	3.60	Agree	7
4. I am interested in our English teacher’s method of teaching.	3.84	Agree	3
5. Our English teacher teaches us to speak in English inside and outside the classroom.	3.66	Agree	5
6. My parents assist me with my English homework and tasks.	2.76	Neutral	10
7. My parents are good speakers of English.	2.88	Neutral	9
8. Communicating with my friends in English helps me enhance my English proficiency.	3.77	Agree	4
9. I like to practice English like native speakers do.	4.00	Agree	2
10. I am fond of watching movies with English subtitles.	4.05	Agree	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.56	Agree	

The results in Table 3.3 displayed the extent of perception of students towards English subject in terms of environmental factors obtained an average weighted mean of 3.56, with a verbal description of “agree.”

Examining the results in more details, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.05 on item no. 10, which states “I am fond of watching movies with English subtitles,” and with a verbal description of “agree.” In contrast, the lowest mean score of 2.76 is on item no. 6, which states “My parents assist me with my English homework and tasks,” and with a verbal description of “neutral.”

Based on the findings of the study, it is significant to find more ways on how to help students who may not receive any help from their parents in answering their English homework. The teachers may provide additional resources or peer study groups to help with each other's homework. In this way, students who have limited parents' assistance at home, might not feel that they are left behind in their task since there is someone who could help them in answering the given tasks. Additionally, a little guidance and words of encouragement from parents could help the learners boost their confidence in learning the English language.

This result aligns with the study of Dadhabai and Kamara (2022) wherein family size is the most important external education environment factor that affect students' academic performance, next is home environment; followed by motivation and role of parent respectively.

Moreover, Clarin et. al (2024) stated that the student's perception of the teacher entailed the teacher's knowledge, attitude, and communication skills with students. This study resulted in the students having a satisfactory perception of their teacher. The teacher's ability to handle the students in English teaching was comprehensive and elicited students' understanding. The learning environment was evaluated based on a variety of factors, such as students' perceptions of the learning environment, which were operationalized as their course experiences and evaluations of teaching; level of academic engagement, skill development, and satisfaction with the learning experience; teacher-student and student-peer interactions and curriculum; perceptions of classroom personalization, involvement, opportunities for and quality of interactions with classmates, organization of the course, and how much instructors make use of more unique methods of teaching and working.

Table 3.4. *Extent of Perception of Students Towards English Subject*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
1. Cognitive factors	3.93	Agree	1
2. Behavioral factors	3.36	Agree	3
3. Environmental factors	3.56	Agree	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.62	Agree	

The data presented in Table 3.4 indicates the extent of perception of students towards English subject which obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.62, with a verbal description of "agree."

Analyzing the results, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 3.93 on cognitive factors with a verbal description of "agree." In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.36 is on behavioural factors with a verbal description of "agree."

Findings in this context suggest that teachers should incorporate interactive activities like peer-group activities that can make English more engaging and relatable to students' life. Motivating students towards the importance of English subject can boost their confidence and positively influence their perception. Connecting English skills to real-life situations may change their behaviour towards the English subject.

This finding aligns with the research conducted by Nguyen and Pham (2020) that the students have average positive attitude towards English. Among the three aspects of language attitudes, the cognitive aspect represents the highest mean score. There is almost no difference between the emotional aspect and behavioral one.

Table 4.1. *Extent of Knowledge of College Students on the S-V Agreement When a Verb Should Agree with its Subject in Number*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	18	4.90	6
20.00 (Poor)	47	12.81	4
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	95	25.89	2
60.00 (Satisfactory)	108	29.43	1
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	61	16.62	3
100.00 (Excellent)	38	10.35	5
Total	367	100.00	

Table 4.1 reveals the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when a verb should agree with its subject in number. The data reveal that most of the respondents belong to a satisfactory level with a frequency of 108 or 29.43%; followed by unsatisfactory indicator with a level of 95 or 25.89%; 61 or 16.62% belong to very satisfactory; 47 or 12.81% belong to poor; 38 or 10.35% belong to excellent; and 18 or 4.90% belong to very poor.

The findings above show that the highest percentage of students with a frequency of 108 or 29.43%, achieved a satisfactory level in understanding subject-verb agreement when a verb should match its subject in number, suggesting a moderate grasp of this concept among most respondents. Conversely, the lowest percentage with a frequency of 18 or 4.90%, falls into the very poor category, highlighting a small group of students who struggle significantly with applying this rule accurately.

Assessing the results, teachers should begin with simplified explanations of the basic S-V agreement rule. This is to provide clear examples on how to distinguish between singular and plural subjects and their corresponding verbs. Interactive activities, such as

sentence construction or real-time error correction exercises, would allow students to practice applying these rules in a low-pressure setting. If consistent formative assessments, such as short quizzes, can monitor the students' progress in their area of confusion.

The findings of this study coincide the statement of Nordquist (2020), a grammatical error is a term used in prescriptive grammar to describe incorrect, unconventional, or controversial usage, such as a misplaced modifier or an inappropriate verb tense. It is also called a usage error. Grammatical errors are usually distinguished from factual errors, logical fallacies, misspellings, typographical errors, and faulty punctuation.

Moreover, the findings coincide with the study of Cadaio et. al (2022) stated that first in rank was Rule No. 1, which states that subject and verb agreement did not agree in number and it has the most prevalent errors. Additionally, the study of Lamela and Reyes (2023) illustrate, the rule on adding "-s" after a noun to make the noun plural is similar to the rule on adding "-s" to a verb in present tense to make it singular. This rule may confuse the ESL learner, especially if the learner has difficulty in identifying the subject and its number.

Table 4.2. *Extent of Knowledge of College Students on the S-V Agreement When One of Two Subjects is Joined by Or, Nor or But*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	14	3.81	6
20.00 (Poor)	44	11.99	4
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	106	28.89	2
60.00 (Satisfactory)	122	33.24	1
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	58	15.80	3
100.00 (Excellent)	23	6.27	5
Total	367	100.00	

Table 4.2 indicates the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when one of two subjects is joined by or, not or but. The data indicate that most of the respondents belong to a satisfactory level with a frequency of 122 or 33.24%; followed by unsatisfactory level with a frequency of 106 or 28.89%; 58 or 15.80% belong to very satisfactory; 44 or 11.99% belong to poor; 23 or 6.27% belong to excellent; and 14 or 3.81% belong to very poor.

Analyzing the results more thoroughly reveals that the highest percentage of students with a frequency of 122 or 33.24%, achieved a satisfactory level in understanding subject-verb agreement (S-V agreement) when one of two subjects is joined by or, nor, or but, indicating a generally adequate grasp of this rule among respondents. In contrast, the lowest percentage with a frequency of 14 or 3.81%, falls into the very poor category, suggesting that a small group of students struggles significantly with this concept.

The result implies that teachers could use focused lessons that clarify how subject choice affects verb agreement in these specific constructions. Through using straightforward examples and visuals to illustrate singular and plural subject combinations, students might not be confused as to what correct form of the verb will be used in the sentence to correspond the number of the subject. Providing hands-on practice through exercises where students identify or correct errors with these conjunctions can help reinforce the concept.

The result corresponds to the outcomes observed in the study by Azmat and Khan (2023). This study provides a detailed analysis of subject-verb agreement errors made by college students in academic writing, focusing on ESL (English as a Second Language) students. It identifies patterns of errors in complex sentences and cases where subjects are joined by conjunctions like "or" or "nor," which can cause confusion in determining singular or plural verbs. Their findings emphasize the importance of targeted grammar instruction to improve accuracy in such constructions, which align with your findings of varied proficiency levels among students.

Another study by Sari, E. A., & Simanjuntak, T. (2022) examines English sentence construction errors, particularly focusing on errors related to subject-verb agreement in compound subjects among college students. They found that a lack of clarity in grammar rules often leads to misapplication, especially in cases with conjunctions like "or" and "nor," where students tend to match the verb with the nearest noun, regardless of the grammatical rules. This study suggests that a structured grammar curriculum can help students master these tricky areas.

Table 4.3. *Extent of Knowledge of College Students on the S-V Agreement When Indefinite Pronouns are Used as Subjects of the Sentence like Every, Each, Everyone, Everybody, Everything, Nobody, Nothing, No one, Anyone, Anybody, Anything, Someone, Somebody, and Something*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	4	1.09	6
20.00 (Poor)	34	9.26	5
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	82	22.34	3
60.00 (Satisfactory)	104	28.34	1
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	99	26.98	2
100.00 (Excellent)	44	11.99	4
Total	367	100.00	

Table 4.3 provides an overview of the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when indefinite pronouns are used as subjects of the sentence like every, each, everyone, everybody, everything, nobody, nothing, no one, anyone, anybody, anything, someone, somebody, and something. The data indicate that most of the respondents belong to a satisfactory indicator with a frequency of 104 or 28.34%; followed by very satisfactory indicator with a frequency of 99 or 26.98%; 82 or 22.34% belong to unsatisfactory; 44 or 11.99% belong to excellent; 34 or 9.26% belong to poor; and 4 or 1.09% belong to very poor.

Delving deeper into the results show that the highest percentage of students with a frequency of 104 or 28.34%, falls into the satisfactory category, showing a fair understanding of subject-verb agreement with indefinite pronouns. In contrast, the lowest percentage with a frequency of 4 or 1.09%, is in the very poor category, highlighting a small group of students who struggle significantly with this concept.

The result implies that teachers should implement small-group sessions or one-on-one tutoring to provide personalized guidance, focusing on common challenges like the tendency to match singular pronouns (e.g., everyone, nobody) with plural verbs. The students should be reminded with the fundamental skills in learning the subject-verb agreement through short quizzes and sentence construction to avoid confusion on the said rules.

The result aligns with the findings of the study by Lamela and Reyes (2023) which stated that the respondents could not determine the number of the indefinite pronouns. They could not grasp the quantity being described by the pronouns. For example, “someone” may be construed as “many” because of the word “some”, so students believed that the pronoun is plural. Similar misapplications may have the same causes.

Similar to the study of Labicane and Oliva (2022), Subject-verb agreement errors and inaccurate use of pronouns were both ranked third among the identified writing mistakes. Some of the participants were unable to observe subject-verb grammatical rules in their outputs.

Table 4.4. *Extent of Knowledge of College students on the S-V agreement when a singular subject followed immediately by as well as, in addition to, no less than, with, together with, or a similar construction*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	22	5.99	6
20.00 (Poor)	47	12.81	4
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	84	22.89	2
60.00 (Satisfactory)	109	29.70	1
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	77	20.98	3
100.00 (Excellent)	28	7.63	5
Total	367	100.00	

Table 4.4 contains a detailed outline of the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when a singular subject followed immediately by as well as, in addition to, no less than, with, together with, or a similar construction. The data indicate that most of the respondents belong to a satisfactory level with a frequency of 109 or 29.70%; followed by unsatisfactory level with a frequency of 84 or 22.89%; 77 or 20.92% belong to very satisfactory; 47 or 12.81% belong to poor; 28 or 7.63% belong to excellent; and 22 or 5.99% belong to very poor.

Examining the results in more details, the highest proportion of students with a frequency of 109 or 29.70%, demonstrated a satisfactory level of knowledge on subject-verb agreement when a singular subject is followed by phrases like "as well as" and "in addition to." In contrast, the lowest proportion is with a frequency of 22 or 5.99% was rated as very poor, indicating limited understanding of this grammatical rule. This suggests that while most students have an adequate grasp, a small portion still struggles significantly with this concept.

These results imply that teachers will focus on strategies that improve understanding of subject-verb agreement with intervening phrases like “as well as” or “together with” could be effective. Since most students achieved only a satisfactory level and a notable portion ranked very poor, a series of examples and more written exercises should be given to students for them to practice. This is to help them clarify how singular subjects remain singular even with intervening phrases. Constant correct practice is significant to improve the students’ knowledge on this rule of subject-verb agreement.

The findings are in line with the research of Nentis (2020), it could be seen from the research findings of his research that the errors were occurred in one of grammatical aspect such as prepositions. The result of this study showed that it was an intralingual transfer that causes the students making errors. The students tend to be confused about the rule of using prepositions. As a result, they made errors by using inappropriate prepositions to the sentences. It could show that the students were still having low grammar ability that cause them cannot specify each function of prepositions in English.

Table 4.5 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when a collective noun is used in the sentence. The data indicate that most of the respondents belong to an unsatisfactory level with a frequency of 104

or 28.34%; followed by satisfactory level with a frequency of 100 or 27.25%; 79 or 21.53% belong to very satisfactory; 43 or 11.72% belong to poor; 31 or 8.45% belong to excellent; and 10 or 2.72% belong to very poor.

Table 4.5. *Extent of Knowledge of College Students on the S-V Agreement When a Collective Noun is Used in the Sentence*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	10	2.72	6
20.00 (Poor)	43	11.72	4
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	104	28.34	1
60.00 (Satisfactory)	100	27.25	2
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	79	21.53	3
100.00 (Excellent)	31	8.45	5
Total	367	100.00	

A closer look at the results indicate that the highest percentage of students, 28.34% (104 respondents), fall into the unsatisfactory category, indicating that a significant portion of students struggle with subject-verb agreement when collective nouns are used in sentences. This suggests that many students have difficulty correctly applying S-V agreement in these contexts. On the other hand, the lowest percentage, 2.72% (10 students), is in the very poor category, representing a small group who have an exceptionally limited understanding of this grammatical rule.

These results highlight that teachers can start by simply explaining how collective nouns (e.g., team, group, audience) may take singular or plural verbs depending on whether the noun is viewed as a single unit or as individuals within the group. Simple, clear examples and exercises can help reinforce this distinction. Interactive activities, like group discussions or sentence correction exercises, would also provide students with opportunities to apply these rules in context.

The findings conformed to the study of Wau (2024). Based on his study, the data analysis showed that average students still made errors on subject-verb agreement in making sentences. It was evidenced by the total of errors made by the students. The students were still confused about distinguishing words which included uncountable nouns as collective nouns as the subject of the sentence.

Table 4.6. *Extent of Knowledge of College Students on the S-V Agreement When Some Nouns End in -S Even Though They Are Considered Singular*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	8	2.18	6
20.00 (Poor)	27	7.36	5
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	62	16.89	4
60.00 (Satisfactory)	108	29.42	1
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	93	25.34	2
100.00 (Excellent)	69	18.80	3
Total	367	100.00	

Table 4.6 outlines the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when some nouns end in -s even though they are considered singular.

The data show that most of the respondents belong to a satisfactory level with a frequency of 108 or 29.42%; followed by very satisfactory level with a frequency of 93 or 25.34%; 69 or 18.80% belong to excellent; 62 or 16.89% belong to unsatisfactory; 27 or 7.36% belong to poor; and 8 or 2.18% belong to very poor.

Based on the results in Table 3.6, the highest level of understanding among college students regarding subject-verb agreement for nouns ending in "-s" but considered singular is at a satisfactory level, with a frequency of 108 or 29.42%. At the other end, the very poor category with a frequency of 8 or 2.18%, represents the lowest level of understanding, suggesting a small proportion of students struggle significantly with this rule.

The outcomes on this matter imply that teachers can focus on common examples, like "news," "mathematics," and "economics," that look plural but are treated as singular. A list of nouns that end with -s but treated as singular should be presented to the students for familiarization. Using activities like sentence corrections or fill-in-the-blank exercises focused on these nouns allows students to practice applying the rule in context. When students are regularly given worksheets on this rule of subject-verb agreement, their skills will be strengthened with these tricky nouns.

The outcome is in line with the work by Grammergeek (2024). When speaking or writing in English, it is vital that you follow the rules of subject-verb agreement. In simple terms, this means making sure that the subject agrees with the verb. By using the correct subject-verb agreement, you will make more understandable and grammatically correct sentences. The rule number nine states that plural form subjects with a singular meaning take a singular verb (such as mumps, home economics, social studies economics, measles, calisthenics, statistics, civics, physics, gymnastics, phonics, news, acrobatics, aesthetics, thesis, mathematics).

Table 4.7. *Extent of Knowledge of College Students on the S-V Agreement When Quantities and Some or Multiples of Numbers are Used in the Sentence*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	13	3.54	6
20.00 (Poor)	40	10.90	4
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	113	30.79	1
60.00 (Satisfactory)	98	26.70	2
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	67	18.26	3
100.00 (Excellent)	36	9.81	5
Total	367	100.00	

Table 4.7 presents a detailed outline of the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when quantities and some or multiples of numbers are used in the sentence. The data present that most of the respondents belong to an unsatisfactory level with a frequency of 113 or 30.79%; followed by a satisfactory level with a frequency of 98 or 26.70%; 67 or 18.26% belong to very satisfactory; 40 or 10.90% belong to poor; 36 or 9.81% belong to excellent; and 13 or 3.54% belong to very poor.

Looking closely at the results, the highest level of knowledge on subject-verb (S-V) agreement with quantities and multiples of numbers is found in the "unsatisfactory" category, with 113 or 30.79% of respondents. This suggests that a small portion of students have a good understanding of how to apply S-V agreement when dealing with such structures. In contrast, the lowest level is in the "very poor" category, where only 13 or 3.54% of the respondents fall.

Delving deeper into the results, the students must be exposed to clear and simple explanations of how S-V agreement works when dealing with collective quantities. Practical examples and exercises that gradually build on this knowledge will help students develop a clearer understanding. To support this learning, interactive grammar exercises, peer reviews, and group discussions can provide valuable feedback and help reinforce correct usage.

Based on the collected data and analysis of Cabaltica and Osabel (2021), the highest frequency errors in subject-verb agreement of the respondents are percent of count nouns requires plural verb.

Table 4.8. *Extent of Knowledge of College Students on the S-V Agreement When the Sentence Has "The Number" and "A Number"*

Indicators (In Percent)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
0.00 (Very Poor)	3	0.82	6
20.00 (Poor)	31	8.45	4.5
40.00 (Unsatisfactory)	85	23.16	3
60.00 (Satisfactory)	125	34.06	1
80.00 (Very Satisfactory)	92	25.07	2
100.00 (Excellent)	31	8.45	4.5
Total	367	100.00	

Table 4.8 displays the extent of knowledge of college students on the S-V agreement when the sentence has "the number" and "a number". The data indicate that most of the respondents belong to a satisfactory level with a frequency of 125 or 34.06%; followed by a very satisfactory level with a frequency of 92 or 25.07%; 85 or 23.16% belong to unsatisfactory; 31 or 8.4% belong to both poor and excellent; and 3 or 0.82% belong to very poor.

Taking a closer look at the results, the highest level is found in the "satisfactory" category, with 125 respondents (34.06%). This suggests that a majority of students have a decent understanding of how subject-verb agreement works in such structures. On the other hand, the lowest score is in the "very poor" category, with just 3 respondents (0.82%). This indicates that only a small number of students struggle significantly with subject-verb agreement in sentences involving "the number" and "a number."

Results about this area imply that students would benefit from focused, practical exercises that clarify these specific terms. The teachers should begin with simple examples that highlight the difference: explain that "the number" typically takes a singular verb (e.g., "The number of students is increasing"), while "a number" takes a plural verb (e.g., "A number of students are attending"). A feedback and corrective exercises should be done regularly to check the students' progress on understanding the rules in subject-verb agreement.

The result conform to the study of Cabaltica and Osabel (2021) which states that the expression "the number" takes on a singular verb while "a number" takes on plural verb is the third frequency errors in subject-verb agreement of the respondents. Below are the wrong examples of respondents with the correct answers inside the parentheses. 1) The number of apples are overripe. (The number of apples is overripe.) 2) A number of high school graduates decreases. (A number of high school graduates decrease.) "Apples" which seems like the subject of the sentence may confuse the respondents, they didn't know that the expression "the number" is also part of the subject and that means, singular verb should be used. Example 2 needs to use a plural verb because the subject uses an expression "a number."

Table 5. Relationship Between the Profile of the Respondents and the Extent of Knowledge of the College Students on the S-V Agreement

Profile of the respondents paired with the extent of their knowledge on the S-V agreement	X2 Computed Value	X2 Tabular Value	df	Level of significance	Decision Rule	Remarks
Age	10.847	21.026	12	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Sex	2.478	7.815	3	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Available learning resources at home	12.202	24.996	15	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho

It is illustrated in Table 4 the relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement. The findings show that the computed chi-square values of age (10.847), sex (2.478), and available learning resources at home (12.202) are lower than the tabular values 21.026 (age), 7.815 (sex), and 24.996 (available learning resources at home). Hence the null hypothesis is accepted indicating that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of knowledge of the college students on the S-V agreement.

The findings above tell that there is no strong evidence that age, sex, and available learning resources at home significantly influence the knowledge of college students on the subject-verb agreement.

According to a study by Park and Kim (2020), age does not significantly affect grammar proficiency in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. They found that while older students may possess broader linguistic experiences, this does not necessarily translate into superior grammatical accuracy in specific areas like S-V agreement.

This result is supported by the study of Cabaltica and Osabel (2021) which found that regardless of sex, students can master the subject-verb agreement when they are motivated and when teachers give them sufficient activities. Students will learn best if they are exposed on the continuous drills and practices.

Moreover, Amante and Andilab (2024) stated that accessibility and availability of learning resources at home will likely depend on the financial situation of learners. The access to resources, such as digital devices, could support learning, it did not directly correlate with specific grammar knowledge, including subject-verb agreement. This suggests that resource availability at home may not significantly influence grammar proficiency.

Table 6. Relationship Between the Perception of the College Students and Their Extent of Knowledge on the S-V Agreement

Variable	Computed R	Tabular R	r2	%1	%2	T-test		Decision Rule	Remarks
						Computed	Tabular		
Relationship between perception of the college students and their extent of knowledge on the S-V agreement	0.1050	0.1046	0.0443	4.43	95.57	2.018	1.984	Reject Ho	Significant

The data indicate the relationship between the perception of the college students and their extent of knowledge on the S-V agreement. The data shows that the computed r-value of 0.1050 is greater than the tabular value of 0.1046 at a 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is significant relationship between the perception of the college students and their extent of knowledge on the S-V agreement.

Studies indicate that perception on students towards the English subject such as cognitive, behavioral, and environmental factors significantly impact students' knowledge of subject-verb agreement (S-V agreement). Cognitive engagement, such as memory retention and attentiveness to grammar rules, alongside behavioral practices like regular grammar exercises, have been shown to improve language proficiency (Park & Kim, 2020). Additionally, environmental factors, including access to learning resources and a supportive home environment, further contribute to better understanding and application of grammar rules (Dolba, 2023). These findings suggest that the interplay of these factors plays a crucial role in shaping college students' grasp of S-V agreement.

Conclusions

This study has investigated the knowledge on subject-verb agreement among college students.

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that most of the respondents are female, 18-19 years old with cellphones as their available learning resources at home. They have positive perception in English subject specifically on aspects of cognitive, behavioural, and environmental factors.

Additionally, most of the students belong to the average level when it comes to the rules of subject-verb agreement, specifically on the following rules: When a verb should agree with its subject in number; When one of two subjects is joined by or, nor, or but; When indefinite pronouns are used as subjects of the sentence like every, each, everyone, everybody, everything, nobody, nothing, no one, anyone, anybody, anything, someone, somebody, and something; When a singular subject followed immediately by as well as, in addition to, no less than, with, together with, or a similar construction; When some nouns end in -s even though they are considered

singular; and When the sentence has “the number” and “a number.”

On the other hand, they are unsatisfactory to the following rules: When a collective noun is used in the sentence; and When quantities and some or multiples of numbers are used in the sentence.

These knowledge on subject-verb agreement of the students are not influenced by their profile such as age, sex, and available learning resources at home. Nevertheless, these S-V knowledge are influenced by their perception towards English subject.

It is recommended that the use of Course Syllabus and Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) should be utilized as significant tools in achieving mastery on the basic rules of subject-verb agreement. Since out of the given eight (8) rules of S-V agreement, only six (6) belong to “satisfactory level,” while two (2) remain at an “unsatisfactory level.”

To enhance the students’ level in these areas, a Course Syllabus and Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) are designed with content that focus the most on the rules wherein the learners struggle the most. These include providing clear explanations, detailed examples, and easy guiding steps in each rule.

It is further recommended that these modules will be used by the teacher and the students during remedial classes for learning instructions and reinforcement activities.

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